

Opportunities and considerations for flexible electronics fabrication using a vinyl cutter

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Abstract

Fablabs have had a major impact on the accessibility of electronics fabrication, alongside innovation in the broader maker movement such as Arduino and Raspberry Pi. From designing and milling custom printed circuit boards, to combining electronics and fabrics to make e-textiles, electronics fabrication is no longer restricted to professionally trained electronic engineers or highly skilled hobbyists. There is, however, a category of electronic device that has yet to see widespread uptake the fablab community: flexible electronics. Rather than describing any electronic circuit that is flexible, flexible electronics normally refers to circuits made from conductive tracks on flexible polymer films, either with or without components. Although flexible electronics manufacturing is an established industry, with applications ranging from e-textiles to soft robotics, there are relatively few documented flexible electronics projects from fablabs. This paper gives an overview of flexible electronics fabrication inside and outside fablabs, and explores potential methods for fablab-based fabrication using a vinyl cutter. Two flexible PCB fabrication methods are presented, and compared to standard techniques. Flexible circuit boards with features as small as 100 μm are demonstrated, along with practical considerations to be taken into account for high quality results, and discussion of needs for future work to properly validate the methods in collaboration with the fablab community.

Keywords

Flexible electronics, vinyl cutter, electronics prototyping

1 Introduction

The term ‘flexible electronics’ sounds like an umbrella term encompassing any electronic device which has parts that can bend. But within the flexible electronics industry, it has quite a specific definition: electronic circuits built on flexible plastic film substrates, with printed or etched conductive tracks, and sometimes containing electronic components. Similar to a conventional, rigid printed circuit board, but with a flexible base material. Common uses of flexible printed circuit boards (flex PCBs) are depicted in Figure 1. Inside cameras, smartphones and other rigid devices, their ability to bend and fold allows dense circuitry to be packed into small spaces, or for rigid parts to be connected by thin strips of flexible circuitry.

Flex PCBs are also used in wearable electronics and e-textiles. They can be bonded onto, or woven into, fabric, as an alternative to using conductive threads or fabrics to create e-textile circuits [1]. They can roll up inside small enclosures to make smart jewellery [2]. In robotics, they can add sensing or additional functionality without adding the weight of a conventional rigid PCB [3]. Flexible PCBs can also be used for many standard electronics applications: they can be made into sensors, heaters, or breakout boards for microcontrollers, LEDs, vibration motors, and much more. They can also serve as flexible cables (flex cables), connecting rigid PCBs together without the need for bulkier wires. Anyone who has ever opened up a laptop or a smartphone will have noticed flex cables joining screens to other PCBs in the device.

With the potential for innovation in so many areas, the ability to make custom flex PCBs could be very useful for many makers and fablab users. As well as making new devices, the ability to make replacement flexible cables for laptops, smartphones or similar devices could contribute to electronics

sustainability by enhancing the reparability of these devices. This paper will review evidence of flex PCBs being made in fablabs, and demonstrate two methods to use a vinyl cutter to fabricate flex PCBs.

Figure 1. Standard applications of flex PCBs: A) Olympus Stylus camera interior, by Steve Jurvetson; B) Front-facing camera smartphone module with flex PCB, by Raymond Spekking; C) Interior of a Panasonic Lumix camera by Steve Jurvetson; D) Flexible circuit embedded in an e-textile garment made by CuteCircuit, image by Becky Stern; E) Flex PCB tactile sensor array for human-robot interaction [3]. All images reproduced under cc-by license terms.

2 Have flexible PCBs been made in fablabs?

To get a sense of the uptake of flexible electronics in fablabs, the Fab Academy and Fabricademy websites were searched for mentions of 'flexible electronics', 'flexible PCB', and 'flex PCB'. This returned only a few results, some of which are shown in Figure 2.

Some are professionally manufactured flex PCBs. Adrian Torres demonstrates a flex PCB breakout board for the Seeed Studio Xiao RP2040 microcontroller, as part of his FabriXiao wearable microcontroller project [4]. Leo Kuipers used a flex PCB pressure sensor in his 'Marimbatron' digital marimba [5]. In this case, the sensor was prototyped using copper tape, before having the final version manufactured.

Other examples are flexible but not strictly within the definition of flex PCBs. Quentin Bolsee and Jack Foreman [6], and later Rehana Al-Soltane [7], used a kerf bending technique to cut FR4 (i.e. rigid PCB material) into a geometry that can bend. Other participants used a vinyl cutter to cut circuits from copper tape, and applied these to flexible substrates. Eduardo Chamorro wrote a tutorial on this

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method, demonstrating a microcontroller breakout on polyvinyl chloride (PVC) sheet [8]. Stephanie Santos made an e-textile glove using thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) [9].

Figure 2. Examples from Fab Academy and Fabricademy. A) Flexible version of FabriXiao by Adrian Torres; B) Flex pressure sensor used by Leo Kuipers; C) User of kerf bending by Quentin Bolsee and Jack Foreman; D) Flexible PCB crown by Rehana Al-Soltane; E) Flex PCB with copper tape by Eduardo Chamorro; F) E-textile glove featuring copper tape circuitry, by Stephanie Santos. All images reproduced under the terms of cc-by licenses.

Taking a broader view, there are some other examples of flex PCB manufacturing in the wider maker community. For example, an Adafruit blog post from 2015 highlights maker Pat Starace's experiments with using a vinyl cutter as part of a DIY flex PCB fabrication process, which is similar to one of the methods presented later in this paper [10]. Another category of electronic device that could loosely be considered flexible electronics is 'paper electronics', where copper tape is applied to paper to create simple circuits. For example, making light-up greeting cards with copper tape, LEDs and a coin cell battery. This method is widely used as a teaching tool. Research by Qie et al later led to the company Chibitronics, which sells 'circuit stickers', which are small flex PCB modules which conductive adhesive on one side, designed to be stuck onto copper tape on paper [11]. Copper tape has also been used by many people to create flexible speaker coils [12]. Conductive pens are another produce which can be used to draw circuits. However, these are not widely used, and it is unclear whether they are compatible with substrates other than paper [13].

Overall, we can conclude that while there are isolated examples of flex PCBs (and similar items) being made in fablabs and in the broader maker community, this practice is not common, and definitely not as widespread as rigid PCB fabrication, which can be done in most fablabs. Of the examples that do exist,

those that are made by the makers, rather than sent off to a PCB manufacturing house, none appear to use industry standard flex PCB manufacturing techniques, which are described in the following section.

3 How are flex PCBs made?

Flex PCB manufacturing processes are broadly the same as those used for rigid boards, except that flex PCBs are too thin for milling or drilling. It is not possible to mill a flex PCB from a copper-plated plastic film, and the copper coatings can be as thin as 18 μm , on flexible substrates ranging from 25 μm to 125 μm . It is possible to print conductive ink onto flexible substrates, using screen printing, inkjet printing or direct ink write printing [14]. However, the silver conductive ink normally used for these processes is expensive, retailing at approximately USD \$100 for a 2 ml cartridge [15]. The ink has a finite shelf life, meaning that buying large quantities to save money only works for high volume industrial production.

The other main fabrication method for flex PCBs is etching a flexible plastic film that has a copper coating, either achieved by electroplating or by using adhesive to laminate a thin copper film onto it. This method is easier than printing techniques to adapt to fablab equipment, and will thus be covered in more detail later.

As an overview, flex PCBs normally consist of the following components:

- A flexible substrate: The amber colour of most flex PCBs is due to the use of polyimide (PI) also known as Kapton, as the substrate. Polyimide is strong, flexible, and can withstand high temperatures, making it compatible with soldering. Polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) are also common. Stretchable substrates such as thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) are also used, although their lower melting temperature makes them less compatible with soldering and other high temperature electronics processes.
- Conductive tracks: metallic tracks are created on the substrate either by printing, or etching a material that has been metal-coated. These tracks are normally made from silver or copper.
- Components: surface mount components are best for flex PCBs, rather than through-hole components, to maintain flexibility and avoid adding significant bulk.
- Coverlay: Thin film, usually made from PI is applied on top of the flex PCB, with openings cut into it to fit around components. It is the flexible version of solder mask used on rigid PCBs, and provides insulation and mechanical support.
- Encapsulation: Encapsulation is adhesive or other material applied on top of components, to prevent them from breaking off when the PCB undergoes bending.

3.1 Standard methods to etch flex PCBs

There are a variety of methods to etch flex PCBs, which vary in terms of cost, availability, and ease of use. The differences are mainly to do with the mask, or resist, which is protects selective areas of copper from etching. They broadly fall into two categories. The first is a transfer method, where the mask is printed on a specialised paper, and then heat pressed or laminated onto the substrate to transfer the printer ink or toner onto the substrate. The second is dry film photolithography, where a photosensitive film is laminated onto the substrate, and then selectively exposed to UV light to develop and harden the film to create the mask. Both techniques are illustrated in Figure 3.

Both of these methods require etching. This involves submersion in a chemical that reacts with any exposed copper and removes it from the substrate, leaving only the copper protected by the mask intact. Ferric chloride is commonly used for this, as is sodium persulphate. Both of these, however, are corrosive chemicals that must be used under strict health and safety controls. It is also possible to etch using salt and vinegar, but this process is significantly slower, taking hours rather than minutes.

There are a couple of barriers preventing the use of these methods in fablabs. Firstly, equipment. The transfer method involves the use of a laminator, which is a common piece of office equipment but is not necessarily found a fablab. There are also relatively few suppliers of transfer kits, and it is unlikely that they are equally accessible in all countries where fablabs are located.

The dry film lithography method is an industry standard and used for high volume production, but it requires a lot of fine-tuning. It is, in this author's view, also time consuming, due to the number of steps in the process, and the fact that after lamination and development of the film, the material must be rested for 30 minutes to 2 hours. It requires a UV exposure box, a high resolution inkjet printer, and ideally an orbital shaker or magnetic stirrer to assist with the development of the photosensitive film.

Figure 3. Standard methods to etch flexible PCBs.

3.2 Newer methods

Recently, new research has demonstrated methods to fabricate flex PCBs without high cost conductive inks or chemical etching, using laser engraving or ablation instead. Standard laser cutters found in fablabs are not normally able to cut copper, due to the fact that copper is highly reflective and thermally. Instead, fibre laser engraving [16] and UV laser ablation [17] can be used.

Even more recently, in March 2025, another method has been proposed, which uses a CO₂ laser to deposit graphite on a polyimide substrate, and then electroplate the copper. As this method starts with a plain polyimide substrate that is not copper plated, it avoids the issues mentioned above associated with copper's reflectivity and thermal conductivity [18].

These new innovations have mostly been produced by researchers and research groups associated with the fablab movement, and may make their way into fablabs in the coming years. But at the moment there is an opportunity to look at flex PCB manufacturing methods using cheaper and more widely available machines.

What is clear at this point is that both standard and newer methods use equipment that is not in the standard fablab inventory, and much of it is expensive, putting it out of reach of many makers (for now at least). Fully realising the potential of flexible electronics means maximising accessibility, and therefore using standard fablab equipment wherever possible.

4 Investigating flex PCB fabrication with a vinyl cutter

This section summarises investigations into flex PCB fabrication carried out by the author over several years, both in her own research and while training others in vinyl cutter operation. Motivated by frustrations with standard flex PCB fabrication techniques, the question ‘Could this be done with a vinyl cutter instead?’ came up repeatedly, and the answer was often ‘Yes!’.

Two fabrication methods are proposed. The claim is not that they are entirely original, as there is evidence of variations on both being demonstrated before. The novelty in this work is in the refining of the techniques, and testing of their limits. Specifically, in using a vinyl cutter to create flex PCBs with features smaller than 1 mm. It is also important to note that this is not a fully comprehensive and quantitative study of these methods. It is preliminary evidence that this is an area with potential for further development in fablabs.

Figure 4 illustrates the two methods. Comparing against Figure 3, it is clear that both involve significantly fewer steps than the standard methods in the previous section.

Figure 4. Fabricating flex PCBs with a vinyl cutter: two methods.

Included in this figure is another major benefit of using the vinyl cutter: the outline of the circuit can be cut at the same time as the mask, or copper tape tracks, are created, resulting in perfect alignment between the two. This is a significant advantage for very small or narrow flex PCBs, particularly those with shapes more complex than a simple rectangle. This is achieved by first cutting the mask or copper tape to create the circuit traces, and then increasing the cutting force to cut through the flexible substrate and create the PCB outline.

Using both of these methods, the question then is: what is the minimum resolution that can be achieved with each fabrication method, and what challenges are associated with each?

5 Findings

Examples of etched flex PCBs are depicted in Figure 5. These include a 1.5 mm wide LED circuit with miniature LEDs (0.6 mm x 0.8 mm) and a flexible breakout board for an AtTiny microcontroller. Weeding, i.e. removing excess vinyl from, the LED circuit was challenging, as the conductive tracks were only 100 μm wide, but it was nonetheless possible. Attempting to create the same circuits using copper tape resulted in the copper tape lifting off the substrate. Circuits with larger features, including the AtTiny breakout depicted in Figures 5B and 5C, were significantly easier to weed.

Figure 5. Successfully etched PCBs using the vinyl mask method. A) narrow LED circuit; B)-C) AtTiny microcontroller breakout board.

A key finding for the copper tape method was that the minimum resolution depends on whether the copper tape is cut on the carrier tape, then transferred to the flexible substrate, or vice versa. This is illustrated in Figure 6A. The coil depicted in Figure 6A, with 1 mm wide traces, was not cut successfully despite optimisation of the cut settings. The solution to this is shown in the right hand side of Figure 6A: applying the tape to the substrate first, and then cutting. The carrier sheet that copper tape is supplied on is designed not to stick to it too strongly, so that the tape can be removed and stuck to something else.

A test cut was carried out to cut rectangles of 5 mm, 4 mm, 3 mm, 2 mm and 1 mm width. As seen in Figure 6B, the 1 mm rectangle came away completely. But if the tape is transferred to the substrate before cutting, the minimum resolution drops from 2 mm to approximately 800 μm . As stated earlier, applying the copper tape to the substrate before cutting also allows for the circuit and the PCB outline to be cut simultaneously, so that they are perfectly aligned.

Figure 6. Troubleshooting copper tape cutting: A) The impact of applying copper tape to the substrate before or after cutting; B) demonstration of the lower limit of 2 mm if the copper tape is to be cut, then transferred; C) AtTiny microcontroller breakout, with 800 μm wide tracks.

As a further challenge, a more complex fine resolution circuit with many corners and small features (100-200 μm) was also cut using both methods. Unsurprisingly, this was not consistently achievable with copper tape, but it was possible to create a vinyl mask and etch it. Achieving this required the 'smoothing' setting on the Roland GS-24 to be turned off. This setting smooths out fine details so that

the cutting blade can move faster, but when cutting small designs, with corners, it can result in some undesired line warping effects. With smoothing turned off, cutting was completed easily. This is seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The impact of the Roland GS-24 smoothing feature on fine details: A) Design; B) Warped lines with smoothing on; C) Accurately cut lines with smoothing off; D) successfully cut vinyl mask; E) failed copper tape cut. Original circuit design by Orlando Hoilett [19].

In terms of other challenges, it was found to be important to have fine, sharp tweezers for successful weeding, to be able to grab on to small pieces of vinyl or copper. Using a roller or squeegee to press the vinyl or copper firmly onto the substrate also helped to create a strong bond, and prevent peeling off during weeding or handling.

All PCB designs used in this work were made or edited using Autodesk EAGLE. While EAGLE and similar software tools are set up to export gerber files for milling or other PCB manufacturing processes, this is not suitable for vinyl cutting and needs to be adapted. Instead, files were printed to PDF, and then opened in Adobe Illustrator. They were then edited to turn traces and pads into paths for cutting, and circuit board outlines were added for the vinyl cutter to cut out the shape of the flex PCB. An example is shown in Figure 8. This particular circuit is an open source potentiostat design created by the Linnes Lab at Purdue University [19].

Figure 8. Adapting the design process for vinyl cutting. Left: original layout; Middle: top layer for vinyl cutting, with lines and shapes converted into outlines for the vinyl cutter to cut along; Right: Bottom layer of circuit adapted for vinyl cutting. Based on a circuit layout by Orlando Hoilett [19]

6 Discussion and future work

Two methods to make flex PCBs using a vinyl cutter have been successfully demonstrated. For quick prototyping, and for all except the smallest circuits, the copper tape method has a clear advantage in

terms of cost, number of process steps, availability of materials, and the fact that it uses only a vinyl cutter and soldering iron to create a functioning PCB. Copper tape can be bought from a variety of sources, in various widths. As it is used in gardening and agriculture to prevent slugs from eating plants, it is widely available in gardening centres and hardware stores in many countries. As copper tape can be stuck to a variety of flexible materials, this method is also not limited to a small number of substrates such as PI and PEN.

The other method, using a vinyl mask to etch flex PCBs, requires additional equipment for etching, but it is able to achieve finer details and a more professional finish overall. It is also likely that flex PCBs manufactured using this method are more flexible, due to the very thin copper layer, and more robust, due to the strength of the adhesive used to stick the copper to the polyimide. However, this would need to be validated through mechanical testing.

Does it matter which machine is used?

Another question to answer is: does the machine that is used matter? These methods should be tested using a variety of different vinyl cutters, to identify whether the results are consistent across different brands, and investigate whether other machines have quirks that are important to be aware of, like the Roland GS-24's smoothing setting.

More complex circuits and more testing

There are also other limitations to consider. At present, these methods are limited to single sided PCBs, which means that it is only possible to make relatively simple circuits. To maximise the potential of this methods, ways to make vias in the flex PCBs will need to be developed. Electrical measurement of the traces would also be a useful way to compare flex PCBs made with a vinyl cutter to professional versions.

Sustainability

While there would be many benefits to seeing more flex PCBs being made in fablabs, sustainability should not be forgotten. The recycling prospects for flex PCBs are unclear, and being able to separate electronic parts from the substrate for reuse or recycling, which may be achievable with copper tape circuits, would be advantageous. Flex PCBs, and similar devices, have also been demonstrated on a mycelium substrate [20], and using carbon-based bioplastics [21]. As biomaterial fabrication is something that many fablabs can do, particularly those which are Fabricademy nodes, there is clear potential for further fablab-based research on bio-based flex PCBs.

Testing with the fablab community

It is also important to note that proving the usefulness of these methods to the fablab community requires user testing on a variety of vinyl cutters in different fablabs, with a range of fablab users, across multiple countries. This may highlight new challenges or areas for improvement, such as variations in local availability of materials, or adjustments to the fabrication process to include fablab users with varying levels of proficiency with vinyl cutter operation.

7 Conclusion

This paper has given an overview of flexible electronics, including fabrication methods, applications, and potential for use in the fablab community. Although there are a small number of examples of flex PCBs being made in fablabs, it is clear that flex PCB fabrication has not been widely adopted within the community. Reviewing the standard methods for flex PCB fabrication, as well as novel methods developed in recent years, highlights what may be a key barrier: accessibility of equipment.

Two methods to make flex PCB with a vinyl cutter have been demonstrated, building on work done by others, and making adjustments to enable fabrication of boards with features as small as 100 μm . There is a need for future work on a) user testing these methods with the wider fablab community, b) more rigorous electrical and mechanical tests on prototypes made using these methods, and c) investigation of more sustainable materials to use as flex PCB substrates. Overall, flex PCB fabrication using a vinyl cutter shows clear potential and will hopefully lead to new fablab-based flex PCB innovations.

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References

- [1] I. Wicaksono *et al.*, 'A tailored, electronic textile conformable suit for large-scale spatiotemporal physiological sensing in vivo', *npj Flexible Electronics*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 5, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41528-020-0068-y.
- [2] 'Ringly Teardown'. Accessed Jul. 07, 2025 [Online]. Available: <https://learn.adafruit.com/ringly-teardown/inside-ringly>
- [3] A. Cirillo, P. Cirillo, G. De Maria, C. Natale, S. Pirozzi, A Distributed Tactile Sensor for Intuitive Human-Robot Interfacing, *Journal of Sensors*, 2017, 1357061, 14 pages, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/1357061>
- [4] A. Torres, 'FabriXiao'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://fabacademy.org/2020/labs/leon/students/adrian-torres/fabrixiao.html>
- [5] L. Kuipers, 'Marimbatron - How Leo Makes (Almost) Anything'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://fabacademy.org/2024/labs/waag/students/leo-kuipers/final-project/>
- [6] 'Flexible capacitive sensor - Fab Academy Quentin Bolsee'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://fabacademy.org/2020/labs/ulb/students/quentin-bolsee/projects/samd11c_flexible_capa/
- [7] 'Rehana's HTMAA'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://fab.cba.mit.edu/classes/863.22/Harvard/people/Rehana/week10.html>
- [8] E. Chamorro, 'Making flexible PCBs with a Vinyl Cutter'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://fabacademy.org/2019/docs/FabAcademy-Tutorials/week04_electronic_production/flexible_pcb_windows_mac.html
- [9] '5. Electronics - Fabricademy Student Website - Stephanie Santos'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://class.textile-academy.org/2019/students/stephanie.santos/assignments/5.%20Electronics/>
- [10] 'Making a Flexible PCB with Pyralux #WearableWednesday « Adafruit Industries – Makers, hackers, artists, designers and engineers!' Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://blog.adafruit.com/2015/02/11/making-a-flexible-pcb-with-pyralux-wearablewednesday/>
- [11] J. Qi, A. Huang, and J. Paradiso, 'Crafting technology with circuit stickers', *Proceedings of IDC 2015: The 14th International Conference on Interaction Design and Children*, pp. 438–441, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1145/2771839.2771873.
- [12] J. Rowland, 'Paper speakers', *Handmade Electronic Music: The Art of Hardware Hacking*, pp. 60–66, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.4324/9780429264818-12/PAPER-SPEAKERS-JESS-ROWLAND.
- [13] Z. Li *et al.*, 'Recent Advances in Pen-Based Writing Electronics and their Emerging Applications', *Adv Funct Mater*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 165–180, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1002/ADFM.201503405.
- [14] S. Khan, L. Lorenzelli, and R. S. Dahiya, 'Technologies for printing sensors and electronics over large flexible substrates: A review', *IEEE Sens J*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 3164–3185, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2014.2375203.
- [15] 'Voltera Conductor 3 - Silver Ink - 2 mL Cartridge'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://store.voltera.io/products/conductor-3-ink-cartridge-2ml>
- [16] Z. Yan, A. Sathya, S. Yusuf, J. M. Lien, and H. Peng, 'Fibercuit: Prototyping High-Resolution Flexible and Kirigami Circuits with a Fiber Laser Engraver', *UIST 2022 - Proceedings of the 35th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1145/3526113.3545652.
- [17] R. Qin *et al.*, 'Flexible Fabrication of Flexible Electronics: A General Laser Ablation Strategy for Robust Large-Area Copper-Based Electronics', *Adv Electron Mater*, vol. 5, no. 10, p. 1900365, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1002/AELM.201900365.
- [18] W. Babatain, C. Park, H. Ishii, and N. Gershenfeld, 'Laser-Enabled Fabrication of Flexible Printed Electronics with Integrated Functional Devices', *Advanced Science*, p. 2415272, 2025, doi: 10.1002/ADVS.202415272.
- [19] 'LMP91000/extras/hardware at master · LinnesLab/LMP91000 · GitHub'. Accessed: Apr. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/LinnesLab/LMP91000/tree/master/extras/hardware>
- [20] D. Danninger, R. Pruckner, L. Holzinger, R. Koeppe, and M. Kaltenbrunner, 'MycelioTronics: Fungal mycelium skin for sustainable electronics', *Sci Adv*, vol. 8, no. 45, p. 7118, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1126/SCIADV.ADD7118/SUPPL_FILE/SCIADV.ADD7118_MOVIES_S1_AND_S2.ZIP.
- [21] M. Koelle, M. Nicolae, A. S. Nittala, M. Teyssier, and J. Steimle, 'Prototyping Soft Devices with Interactive Bioplastics; Prototyping Soft Devices with Interactive Bioplastics', p. 16, doi: 10.1145/3526113.3545623.